

THE IMAGE OF RIVERS IN UZBEK LITERATURE (IN THE WORKS OF OMON MATJON)

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Abstract. *This article examines the artistic representation of river imagery in Uzbek literature through the works of Omon Matjon. It is demonstrated that, within the national literary tradition, the depiction of rivers rises to the level of a symbolic artistic image. Particular attention is paid to the poet's mastery of image creation, especially his original interpretation of the Amu Darya as a river of vital significance to the life of the people. The study analyzes the poet's lyrical works in which the image of the Amu Darya functions as a means of expressing the author's inner experiences, ideas, philosophical reflections, as well as his dreams and aspirations. The findings of the research contribute to identifying the role and importance of artistic psychologism in contemporary Uzbek literature and to a deeper understanding of the literary process.*

Keywords: *Uzbek literature, river imagery, Amu Darya, Omon Matjon, lyric poetry, artistic image, artistic psychologism.*

Introduction

Literature is a means of representing life through artistic images and expressive devices. No other form of art can portray the human psyche, emotions, and inner experiences as accurately and convincingly as literature. In Uzbek literature, the depiction of natural elements, particularly rivers, holds significant artistic and aesthetic value. The image of the river is widely used as a symbol of historical memory, a source of life, and a metaphor for time and destiny.

From ancient times, major rivers such as the Amu Darya and the Syr Darya have occupied an important place in both written and oral Uzbek literature. These rivers are portrayed not merely as geographical objects but as artistic images with deep symbolic and metaphorical meanings. In folklore, river imagery is also vividly represented. For example, in the epic *Kuntug'mish*, episodes such as Kholbeka's portrait floating in a chest on the river and Kuntug'mish losing his children in the river clearly demonstrate the symbolic role of rivers. In the epic *Tohir and Zuhra*, the river is depicted as a means of salvation when Tohir is set adrift in a chest. Numerous folk songs also incorporate images of rivers.

In classical Uzbek literature, particularly in the works of Alisher Navoi, the river is interpreted as a symbol of the continuity of life, the flow of time, and the changeability of human destiny. In Navoi's writings, water and river imagery represent divine purity and spiritual perfection. Rivers also serve as a means of expressing emotional states such as longing, separation, and union. Thus, river and water images in Navoi's works symbolize life, time, divine purity, and spiritual growth.

In Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's *Baburnama*, rivers such as the Amu Darya, Syr Darya, Kohak, and Zarafshan are described from a historical and geographical perspective, while also being portrayed as essential sources of life. Mashrab associates the image of the river with mystical and spiritual experiences. In Cho'lpon's works, river imagery reflects national destiny, the idea of freedom, and inner suffering.

Overall, the image of the river in Uzbek literature functions as a depiction of nature, a symbolic image, a tool of artistic psychologism, and a means of philosophical reflection. Writers of each historical period have enriched this image in accordance with their worldview and the spirit of their time. In twentieth-century Uzbek literature, river imagery gained new ideological and aesthetic significance. In Jadid literature and later poetry, rivers were depicted in close connection with social changes, people's lives, and national awakening.

Gafur Gulom links the image of the river with social reality and the life of the people. In his work *Shum Bola*, river imagery helps to reveal the difficult living conditions of the time and the psychological state of the protagonist. The river becomes an obstacle that prevents the hero from moving forward, while returning is equally impossible, thereby symbolizing life's hardships and inner conflict.

*Daryo toshqin ,suvlar to 'lqin
O 'tolmayman yor-yor,
Otim oriq ,manzil uzoq
Yetolmayman yor-yor. .*

*The river is flooded, the waters are wavy.
I cannot cross, dear.
My horse is thin, the destination is far.
I cannot reach it, dear.*

Oybek portrays the Amu Darya and Syr Darya in harmony with historical processes and the spirit of the age. In modern Uzbek poetry, river imagery increasingly serves to express personal emotions, inner psychological states, and philosophical reflections. Mirtemir depicts rivers as symbols of labor, life, and human destiny. In Ibrayim Yusupov's *Jayhun Shamollari*, the Amu Darya is described as a great and mighty river, while the wind blowing from it is compared to an eternal breeze, emphasizing the idea of continuity and permanence.

Especially in the works of Omon Matjon, the image of the Amu Darya is interpreted as a central artistic symbol. The poet presents the river as a representation of the people's destiny, historical memory, and spiritual strength. In his lyrical works, the Amu Darya serves as a means of expressing inner emotions, aspirations, and philosophical reflections on life. Through river and water imagery, themes such as the homeland, time, and the transience of human existence are conveyed. Thus, the poet successfully uses the image of the river to artistically reveal national consciousness, historical memory, human emotions, and the challenges of the era.

Omon Matjon always took pride in being a native of Khorezm. He had a deep knowledge of the history of Khorezm, and every inch of its land was precious to him. Every plant growing in the oasis and every bird flying in its sky were dear to the poet. Above all, the Amu Darya—the lifeline of the oasis—was as close to him as a mother. For this reason, the image of the Amu Darya appears in almost all of his poems. While creating the image of the invincible and persistent Amu Darya, the poet presents the river, like the people themselves, as possessing a long history and containing countless layers of wisdom within its depths.

In some poems, the Amu Darya is portrayed as a strong and powerful young man endowed with great energy, while in others it appears as an old man weary of witnessing the cruelty of the world and humanity, having turned away from life. Water is traditionally regarded as a symbol of honesty and purity, and in the poet's perception, the Amu Darya is a place of spiritual purification. In the poem "*The Last Plea of Amir Alim Khan*," the Amu Darya is depicted precisely as such a sacred place.

Amir Alim Khan is a historically real figure. Having abandoned the throne of Bukhara, which he once ruled, he fled to Afghanistan. There, having grown old and gone blind toward the end of his life, Amir Alim Khan asks his children to take him to the banks of the Jayhun (Amu Darya). In the poem, the river is likened to a mother.

*Yana u aytdiki : "Ona daryoning,
So 'ng bora tuyayin shaxtin ,nafasin.
Ergashtirib kelsa zora to 'lqinlar*

*And then he said:
"Mother river,
Let me feel once more your frost, your breath.*

Yurtimdan biron-bir narsaning sasin.....”

*Perhaps the waves may bring along
The faint scent of something from my
homeland...”*

The river is portrayed as a source of salvation and power, beloved like one’s homeland and people. The poem depicts the helpless final state of a ruler who spent his life struggling for power and luxury, but when the time came, abandoned his state to save himself.

The rapid turning of fate is emphasized: a king who once ruled a vast empire becomes a wanderer in foreign lands, deprived of his homeland. This fate was self-inflicted, yet he realizes too late that remaining with one’s people and homeland until the last breath is itself a great blessing. At the same time, the poet reminds the reader that the waves of the river also carry the cries of those who were oppressed in harems and prisons and those who wandered homeless as victims of the Amir’s tyranny. The poet stresses that the ruler’s desire to reach the river is not merely nostalgia, but a wish to cleanse himself of his sins.

Through this image, the poet addresses his people, urging them that whoever is to be raised to the throne should be taken to the Amu Darya for purification before spiritual blindness overtakes them. The concept of “blindness” is used in two senses: literal blindness and moral blindness caused by power, arrogance, and greed. Both meanings function simultaneously within the poem.

*Xalqim! Tilsiz bardosh ham umid bilan
Kimniki ko’tarsang taxti a’loga,
Hali ko’zlari ko’r bo’lmasadan burun
Tavofga olib bor Amudaryoga!*

*My people! Even silent endurance is bound
with hope.
Whomever you raise to the highest throne,
Before his eyes grow blind,
Take him on pilgrimage to the Amu Darya!*

The poet introduces an innovative interpretation by using the concept of the “Mother River,” identifying the Amu Darya as such. This metaphor reflects Omon Matjon’s imaginative power and artistic mastery. The maternal status of the river in his works is not accidental: as long as the river exists, life continues. Plants, insects, animals, and all existence are born and sustained through the river. The water of the river is the source of life and livelihood. Just as raising a hand against one’s mother is considered a grave sin, treating the river with ingratitude is also regarded as sinful. The poet anxiously emphasizes that the crisis of rivers signifies a crisis of humanity itself.

In his poetic narrative “*Times When One Can Speak*,” Omon Matjon depicts the river drifting far from its original banks, failing to reach the Aral Sea, and vividly portrays the tragic consequences of this separation. The image of the Mother River suffering from the recklessness and irresponsibility of her children is powerfully conveyed. The comparison between the historical significance of the river and its present condition creates a deeply tragic image of a dying river.

This serves as a warning to the reader, reminding them that losing the river is akin to losing one’s mother.

*Tarix bo’yi necha shoirlar suyib,
“Asov, buyuk, loyqa, telba, jayhun,
darbadar...”
kabi o’nlab sifatlarga yo’g’irgan nahr
Orolga ham yetmay qolgan edi bu zamon,
o’lganimni go’yo hech kim ko’rmasin deya
o’z joyidan olis ketgan it misol.....”*

*Throughout history, so many poets have loved
it,
Draping the river in dozens of epithets —
“Fierce, great, turbid, mad, Jayhun, a
wandering outcast...”
Yet in our time, this river could not even
reach the Aral Sea,
As if wishing that no one would witness its
death,*

Like a dog that strays far from its place to die alone...

The poet emphasizes that the tragedy of the river is not the tragedy of a single individual, but of an entire nation. He warns that such irresponsibility may lead to irreversible climatic changes on Earth and that innocent future generations will bear the consequences of today's negligence. Through deep emotional concern, the poet calls humanity to awareness and responsibility.

*Xo 'sh ,daryoda bu fojia battar zo 'raysa,
horg 'in Orol yillar sayin uzoqlab, ozib,
Xorazmga tog 'misoli xizmat qiluvchi,
ya 'ni voha iqlimiga qalqonlik etgan,
zarur namchil, zich havosi siyraklay bersa ,
Ne kechadi bu joylarning holi, xo 'sh, ayting?!*

*So, if this tragedy in the river grows even worse,
The weary Aral gradually recedes and shrinks year by year,
Depriving Khorezm of its mountain-like service,
That is, the protection it gave to the oasis climate,
Reducing essential moisture and thinning its dense air,
What will become of this land's condition, tell me, what then?!*

In contrast, in the poem "Amu," the image of the river is portrayed differently. Here, the river is depicted as a young son full of strength, striving toward the future. It has clear goals and aims to reach distant and vast lands in order to create a new future there. Neither lowlands nor stubborn cliffs can hinder it. The river is determined to achieve its objectives. In this poem, the Amu Darya rises to the level of a generalized image embodying human qualities.

*Qarang, telba desalar hamki,
O 'z yo 'lida toymas u zinhor,
Go 'yo taqir huv kengliklarda
Ko 'zlagani katta baxti bor.*

*Look, even if they call it mad,
It never tires on its path, certainly,
As if in the vast emptiness
It carries a great fortune it seeks.*

Historically, it is well known that many scientists who made great discoveries were once accused of madness, yet over time their contributions proved vital to humanity. Similarly, the river's aspiration to reach new worlds across barren lands may appear irrational, but its goal is clear and its strength sufficient. Omon Matjon skillfully employs the image of the river to convey his creative intentions with high artistic mastery.

Such portrayals enhance the aesthetic and ideological significance of river imagery in Uzbek literature. Rivers are compared to the happiness and fortune of the Uzbek people. The lyrical hero takes pride in possessing rivers, considering them a symbol of spiritual wealth. For the poet, rivers are not merely natural objects but bonds that connect ancestors with future generations, transmitting moral values across time. In his poetry, rivers are elevated to the level of sacred concepts, preserved with faith-like purity.

*Sendan xabar keltirsa,
Amudaryo ,Sirdayo.
Derdim,aziz diyorda,
Mening qo 'sh baxtim bor-da!*

*If it brings news from you,
Amu Darya, Syr Darya.
My sorrow, in this beloved land,
My double happiness is there!*

In conclusion, the depiction of rivers in Omon Matjon's works transcends simple natural scenery and acquires profound symbolic and philosophical meaning.

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